

UTERINE FIBROIDS - CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS

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Abstract: *Uterine fibroids are a frightening diagnosis for any woman. Such a decision by an ultrasound diagnostic doctor will frighten even the most resilient women. However, you should not worry about the risk of sudden fibroids.*

Key words: *Uterine fibroids, neoplasms, ultrasound examination, Chronic stress condition.*

First, in the next menstrual cycle, it is necessary to consult another specialist and repeat the ultrasound examination (ultrasound). What is uterine fibroids, why does it occur, how can fibroids be treated conservatively and surgically, and what are its symptoms? Let's talk about it in more detail.

Uterine fibroids are benign neoplasms (tumors) in the walls of the uterus or cervix. It is also sometimes called fibromyoma or leiomyoma. In many cases, there are many foci of fibroids in the uterus, each of which varies in size from a few millimeters to several centimeters. To express the size of a fibroid, gynecologists use a comparative measurement of the size of the uterus in women at different stages (weeks) of pregnancy.

The development of uterine fibroids is often associated with hormonal disorders in women, especially with increased estrogen concentrations. This hormonal disorder is more common in young women of childbearing age. Due to the natural decrease in estrogen hormones during menopause, uterine fibroids can disappear on their own, regardless of treatment. In addition, the causes of uterine fibroids can be:

Hereditary predisposition;

Hormonal disorders;

Adenomyosis;

Inflammation of the genitals;

Metabolic diseases (including diabetes);

Chronic systemic diseases;

Inactive lifestyle, overweight;

Chronic stress condition;

Effects of abortion, use of intrauterine (intrauterine) contraceptives;

Sexual dissatisfaction (anorgasmia during sex).

Fibroids are hormone-dependent diseases. Uterine fibroids are less likely to develop when the level of female hormones in the body is low, that is, before puberty and after menopause. Excessive levels of estrogen hormones can lead to the development of fibroids.

However, it should also be taken into account that all hormones in the human body are interdependent, and often uterine fibroids can occur not only due to high estrogen concentrations, but also due to a delicate imbalance of all hormones of the female reproductive system. Endogenous estrogen-like substances have been identified in the human body, and uterine fibroids are as sensitive to them as estrogens. These substances are called xenoestrogens and their presence can also contribute to tumor formation.

Often, women do not suspect the presence of fibroids and may not show any external symptoms. Therefore, in many cases, a woman is diagnosed with fibroids only when she visits a gynecologist for a completely different reason or during a medical examination. If the uterine fibroids are large, the symptoms are almost always recorded, otherwise there are no signs and symptoms.

Symptoms of uterine fibroids:

The symptoms of uterine fibroids are very similar to the symptoms of many other diseases of the reproductive organs. Therefore, if any of the following symptoms are detected, it is important not to delay a visit to the gynecologist to make a definite diagnosis.

Symptoms of uterine fibroids can include:

- Irregular menstruation, bloody discharge in the middle of the cycle;
- Rarely, uterine bleeding occurs, sometimes with excessive bleeding;
- Disorders of urination, frequent urination (associated with increased intra-abdominal pressure due to a large tumor);
- Long-term infertility, both primary and secondary;
- Lower abdominal pain, feeling of tightness;
- Abdominal enlargement not associated with weight gain.

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